

Research

Bi-Directional LSTM Machine Learning Based Model for Chinese Word Segmentation

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Abstract : Word Segmentation has done wonders and usually been considered within Natural Language Processing (NLP). However different languages have different writing systems, which involves an enormous words with numbers of the characters. Even with characters, they have even smaller elements that usually goes unnoticed or difficult to deal. In our paper, here we are going to propose the concept for segmentation of the words with the help the Bi-directional LSTM which is a part of the Recurrent Neural Network to figure out the sub-character level illustration and to observe into the vast layer of the linguistics. We are going to take Chinese word Segmentation as experiment case. We have include the model that are more likely to be a suitable for our paper that includes LSTM and LSTM with a Conditional Random Field (CRF) layers. These are essential for evaluating our dataset results as we will be experimenting it in python programming. With this paper, we were able to get 96.64% accuracy in CITYU as compare to 95.4% (Cai et al. 2017) , while we were able to get 94.65% accuracy in MSR as compare to 93.9% (Zheng et al. 2013).

Keywords: Chinese Word Segmentation(CWS), Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), Bi-directional Long Short Term Memory (Bi-LSTM), BIES tokens, CITYU, MSR and PKU datasets, Hyper Parameters

Introduction

We know there are vast number of languages in this world. Different languages have different style of writing of the words. Mostly English language, words are easy to determine as it are written with different boundaries. Unlike English words, most of the Asian languages, words are written without boundaries. Coming to the Asian words, Chinese words also use the same rules or patterns. So to segment the words, it requires a big challenge which is completely different

from the English Words. As we know, Deep Learning have become a hugely success along with neural network have shown the vast capability in Natural Language Processing Tasks.

Previously, most of the Chinese word Segmentation approaches has been worked as stand-alone task and applied in the general domain of formal text such as technical articles. [1], [2] CWS is mostly treated as a character based sequence labeling task (Xue et al., 2003; peng el al., 2004).[3] As mention by W.B Jiang, L Huang and Q. Liu, there havepurposed structured perceptron. They have presented an automatic annotation adaptation strategy to provide the better result in CWS and POS tagging.[4]The Joint Chinese word Segmentation, POS tagging and parsing approach have been developed where each individual model was separately trained and incorporated together in a unified framework with decoding(Xiaoqing Zheng, Hanyang Chen, and Tianyu Xu. 2013). Besides modeling word representation directly, sequential labeling is another popular approach. [5]For instance, WenzhePei et al. (2014) predict the label of a character based context for the CWS. In the paper, he have applied the neural network to CWS and achieved a performance that approaches the state-of-the-art methods.Many experiment have been conducted where we can see most recent research have shown that RNN have perform better than previous popular algorithm.There is also have been approach of using LSTMs which help to take the information about potential long distance data by Chen et al.

Basically, Chinese Word segmentation is the separation of the characters from the words with the boundaries.It make us easy to understand the meaning of the characters of the words and we can separate the characters with a meaning attached to it. We are going to perform our Word segmentation with the help of LSTM, BI-LSTM along with CRF to get the effective result for our experiments. We have taken and compare our model with the past work model algorithms like the neural probabilistic models performed by Bengio et al., 2003. [6] They have used HHMM to different lexical tasks including word segmentation along with POS tagging with unknown words recognition and disambiguation. As model of Chen et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2017 have been successful with LSTM model, [7] Ji Ma 2018 have use the state of the art for the CWS using Bi-LSTM

Mostly our work are performed in the datasets provided by BACKOFF 2005. Here for our research, we will be using three datasets.

- CityU These are the datasets from City University of the Hong Kong
- MSR These are the datasets from Microsoft Record Open Data
- PKU These are the datasets from Peking University

We have performed and show that with a proper training and tuning a certain architecture with a minimal feature set, we are able to get good results. With this paper, we have described the designed experiments on MSR, PKU and CITYU benchmark datasets. We have received good accuracy as well as other essential performance in the experiment.

Neural Network Model

Here, we are going to state our used model for the experiments. We have done the models of RNN, CRF, LSTM, BI-LSTM and BI-LSTM-CRF. We will explain the details in this section.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)

RNN are the types of neural networks designed for extracting information from sequences/time series data. RNN have produce a significant result in related with language model.

Figure 1: Simple RNN

Here we can have Dropout and Pretrained Embedding.

Dropout

[8] Similar to the Dropout by Srivastava 2014, we can also apply dropout strategies to find the effectiveness to avoid overfitting. It is very useful for reduction of over fitting in neural networks and helps in reducing complex training data. We use dropout in our model. We have dropout rate is fixed to 0.6

Pre-trained Embedding

Pre-trained embedding helps to achieve better performance of neural networks in Chinese Word Segmentation. [9][10] It can be also seen in the paper done by Chen et al., 2015a, Chungqi Wang et al., 2017. It is very effective technique which has been used in many Neuro-Linguistic

Programming (NLP) problems. We can perform the experiments on pretraining embeddings as a pleasant tuning on the datasets

Conditional Random Field (CRF)

CRF is use mostly for the sequence labeling task in our model. It basically helps to decode the most efficient sequences of the labels that are the provided in input sentences. It can predict the distributed tags for each steps which later is decoded to get optimal tag sequences. In CRF, inputs and outputs are co-related with each other. CRFs produces the greater tagging accuracy. While training the data, we can minimized loss with help of back propagation. We can also use Veterbi algorithm to get the label sequence with more effective result. [11]One of the similar method of CRF is Maximum-entropy Markov Model (MEMM), which was proposed previous by Zhang 2003.

$$p\frac{y}{x} = \frac{1}{Z(x)} \prod_{t=1}^T \exp\left(\sum_{k=1}^k \theta_k f_k(y_t, y_{t-1}, x_t)\right)$$

Where y is the hidden state and x is the variable which were observed.

Long Short Term Memory (LSTM)

Figure 2: LSTM unit

LSTM units are composed of 4 main elements. Memory cell or information cell is responsible to hold the data and three gates to find the flow of the data inside the LSTM. Three gates that are as follows

- Input Gate – Responsible for writing the data into the memory cell
- Output Gate – Reads the data from information cell and send back to the RNN
- Forget Gate- Maintains/Delete Data from the information cell

These gates are similar structure to the neural in traditional neural network. Since they are multiplication of analogues sigmoid activated nodes. By manipulating these gates, our current network is able to remember what it needs and forget what is no longer useful. In figure, we can see the data input and the network state are directly connect to all the gates so each gate received the same information as recurrent net processing cell The LSTM helps to capture potential long-distance dependencies along with it can keep previous information in memory which are useful.

Figure 3: Procedure of LSTM

Information from previous hidden state and information from the current input are pass through the sigmoid function. Values come up between 0 and 1. Those which are close to 0 means forget and those close to 1 means to keep. To update the cell state, we have the input stage. First we pass the previous hidden state and current input into sigmoid function that decide which values will be updated by change forming value between 0 and 1. Zero means not important while one means important. You also pass the hidden state and current input into the tan function to get the value between negative one (-1) and positive one (+1). This helps to regulate the network. Then

we will multiply the tan output with sigmoid output, the sigmoid output will decide which information to keep from the tan output

$$C_t = f_t \times C_{t-1} + i_t \times C1_t$$

Where, C_{t-1} = previous cell state, f_t = forget gate output, i_t = input gate output, $C1_t$ = candidate, C_t = hidden state

Bi-LSTM-CRF

We are going to combine both Bi-directional LSTM along with CRF. Here, we can use level tagging information of a sentence with a help of CRF layer while LSTM layer is useful to use the past input features.

Bi-directional Long Short Term Memory (Bi-LSTM)

Figure 4: Bi-directional LSTM

As shown in the figure, we going to use Bidirectional LSTMs are similar to the LSTM but Bi-LSTM can help to improve the model performance in a sequence labeling or sequence tagging task. Bidirectional LSTM runs the input in two methods, that is from past to the future and from future to the past. That means, it runs backwards which helps to preserve the data or instructions from the future. Bi-directional LSTM enable you to use both the hidden states together so that you will be able go to any time. Going to any time in states means we are able to preserve the required instructions both from the past and the future. Bi-LSTM improves on this as it stacks a reversed LSTM on the data as well.

Training Methods of Model and General Solution Architecture

In this section, we are going to describe the training method of our datasets. We know Chinese word segment is considered as a sequence labeling of the character. We have assigned the character and labeled them into 4 different label for the segmentation. In another words, we can create the labelled training set into one of the four tokens. They are B, I, E, S where B stands for Begin, I stands for In-between, E stands for End while S stands for Single of the multicharacter segmentation.

Figure 5: Word Segmentation Model

First we will provide a unique number to all the characters of the words which we are going to segment. Those are then pass through Embedded Layer. Those are pre-trained embedded layers. Once it is pass, our Bi-directional LSTM network will be used which decide whether to take data from the past or from the future. It will perform propagation of Backward and Forward. After that it will be pass to the BIES through Hidden state. We need to have a digital pattern along with letter pattern and mark pattern. While segmentation of the Chinese word, we can encounter with numbers like 0 to 9 along with the special characters like +, % etc. We can also encounter with the English letters from A to Z along with other special characters. We can use special functions to solve this one. We will provide the corpus class. We can provide the training and

testing path for our model. We have also define the tokenization of the file along with building a Vocabulary class where we can initialize add and trim of the words. We will configure RNN with dropout. We will then use encoder for embedding. We will configure embedding size. We will provide the range for it. We will provide the input size as embedding size, hidden size and configure the n number of layers. We going to use the Hyper Parameters for the training the datasets.

Since training algorithm learns the parameters from data, we are going to train different setting for the manually tuned hyper parameter grid for each evaluation we done for our configuration. We can get the different initial learning rate, input and dropout rates along with learning rate schedule. We have provided batch size set to 128, test batch size set to 16. We choose our hyper parameters according to the average performance from our developed sets.

General Solution Architecture involves mostly 4 parts. Those are as follows

Figure 6: General Solution Architecture

- Look Up table
 - Character embedding
 - Dimension: d
- Concatenate

- Dimension: $k*d$ (k is the window size)
- Hidden Layer
 - Dimension: hyper parameter
- Output Layer
 - Dimension: 4 corresponding labels

Character Embedding

- We are going to use the neural network in order to process the symbolic data which will be represent into distributed vectors (embedding)
- Use a Character Dictionary that is extracted from training the data.
- Those unknown words which are not recognize are converted into a special symbols

With the help of the LSTM and Bi-LSTM as mention above in our models for the neural networks, we will train the datasets for the experiments.

Experiments and Results

Arranging Datasets

Here we have taken the datasets from Backoff 2005 where we have evaluate our model which contain MSR, PKU, and CITYU datasets. We have trained all our model in NVIDIA GeForce MX150. We trained our datasets around 7-8 hours in GPU while CPU took much more time depending on training datasets (more than 1 day). Mostly in the paper, we will take the data from GPU. We also varies our embedding and batch size so that we can get our result little faster. For all our datasets, we have given 10% for the testing our result while 90% is for training the data.

We will compare our work with previous neural models of Zheng 2013, Pei 2014 and chungqi wang 2017.

Majorly, we are going to check the Recall, F1-score, Precision and Accuracy from the training of the datasets. For evaluation of the results, we have taken 4 metrics as a consideration. They are as follows

- Precision

Precision is a certain parts of the fetched documents that are important to the query. It can be formulated as the number of the accurate results upon the number of all possible returned results.

$$Precision = TruePositives \div (TruePositives + FalsePositives)$$

- Recall

They are certain parts of the relevant documents which are successfully retrieved. It can be formulated as the number of accurate outcome upon the number of outcome that should have returned.

$$Recall = TruePositives \div (TruePositives + FalseNegatives)$$

- F-Score

F-score can be recognized by the name as F1 score or F-measure. It uses both the recall and Precision for the calculation. They are evenly weighted in F-score.

$$F - score = 2 \times ((Precision * Recall) \div (Precision + Recall))$$

- Accuracy

It is the method where we going to check what percentage of our model got right. It can be formulated as the number of accurate predictions upon the total numbers of the predictions.

$$Accuracy = ((TP + TN) \div (TP + TN + FP + FN))$$

Table (a) shows our configuration of the model.

Parameters	Value
Windows Size	50
Windows Step	25
Batch Size	128
Embedding Size	16
Hidden Size	200
Dropout Rate	0.6
Initial Range	0.1

Table (a): Configuration

After evaluating our models, we get the following results for our 3 datasets. The result is shown in following table (b)

Datasets	Precision	Recall	F-score	Accuracy
CITYU	97.28%	96.96%	97.12%	96.54%
MSR	95.44%	95.43%	95.43%	94.65%
PKU	95.42%	94.00%	94.15%	94%

Table (b): BI-LSTM Result

In the below table (c), we are showing the result of our testing model with CRF.

Datasets	Precision	Recall	F-score	Accuracy
CITYU	97.78	97.50	97.76	97.16
MSR	96.10	96.40	96.50	95.40
PKU	96.45	96.25	96.40	96.15

Table (c): BI-LSTM with CRF Results

We can compare our result with the previous models. We can see it in following table (d)

Models	Datasets			Precision	Recall	F1-score
	CITYU	MSR	PKU			
				92.8%	92%	92.4%
(Zheng et al. 2013)	-	93.9%	92.8%	-	-	-
(Pei et al.,2015a)	-	-	94.5%	-	-	-
(Cai et al. 2017)	95.6%	-	-	-	-	96.8
(Pei et al., 2014)	-	-	-	93.2%	93.4%	93.5%
Our Model	96.54%	94.65%	94%	97.28%	96.96%	97.12%

Table (d): Comparison Table

Conclusion

Bi-LSTM improves on this as it stacks a reversed LSTM on the data as well. We have used the Neural Network Bi-directional LSTM to train the datasets for the Chinese Word Segmentation.

With the help of the SIGHAN Backoff 2005 datasets, we were adept to conduct the experiment where we are able to get the efficient result in term of accuracy and precision of the work. Also, with the help of the Dropout, pre-embedding and hyper-parameters, we were able to get the good result in the sequence labeling task. While, we were capable to get the efficient result on the experiments of those datasets, more efforts and new methods can be used since deep neural network works well for the Word Segmentation.

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Reference

1. Chinese Word Segmentation as Character Tagging by Nianwen Xue Vol.8 ,No.1, 2003
2. Chinese Segmentation and New Word Detection using Conditional Random Field by Fuchun Peng 2004.
3. W.B Jiang, L Huang and Q.Liu “Automatic adaption of annotation standards: Chinese word segmentation and POS tagging – a case study,” in Proceedings of ACL/AFNLP,2009
4. Deep Learning for Chinese Word Segmentation and POS Tagging by Xiaoqing Zheng, Hanyang Chen and Tianyu Xu.
5. Wenzhe Pei, Tao Ge, and Chang Baobao. 2014. Maxmargin tensor neural network for Chinese word segmentation. In proceedings of ACL.
6. YoshuaBengio, R´ejeanDucharme, Pascal Vincent, and Christian Janvin. A neural probabilistic language model. The Journal of Machine Learning Research, 3:1137-1155, 2003.
7. State-of-the-art Chinese Word Segmentation with Bi-LSTMs by Ji Ma, KuzmanGanchev , David Weiss (Google AI language)
8. Nitish Srivastava, Geoffrey Hinton, Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Ruslan Salakhutdinov.2014. Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. The journal of Machine Learning Research , 15(1):1929-1958
9. Improving Chinese Word Segmentation and POS Tagging with Semi-supervised Methods using Large Auto-Analyzed Data by YiouWang,JunichiKazama,YoshimasaTsuruoka,Wenliang Chen, Yujia Zhang and KentaroTorisawa.
10. Convolutional Neural Network with Word Embeddings for Chinese Word Segmentation by Chunqi Wang and Bo Xu
11. Chinese Lexical Analysis Using Hierarchical Hidden Markov Model by Hua-Ping Zhang, Qun Liu, Xue-Qi Cheng , Hao Zhang, Hong-kui Yu.

12. [Mikolov et al.2010] T. Mikolov, M. Karafiat, L. Burget, J. Cernocky, and S. Khudanpur. 2010. Recurrent neural network based language model. INTERSPEECH. [Collobert et al.2011] R. Collobert, J. Weston, L. Bottou, M. Karlen, K. Kavukcuoglu and P. Kuksa. 2011. Natural Language Processing (Almost) from Scratch. Journal of Machine Learning Research (JMLR).
13. Bidirectional LSTM-CRF models for sequence tagging by Z Huang, W Xu, K Yu- 2015
14. Changning Huang and Hai Zhao. Chinese word segmentation: A decade review. Journal of Chinese information Processing, 21(3):8-20, 2007.
15. Deng Cai, Hai Zhao, Zhisong Zhang, Yuan Xin, Yongjian Wu, and Feiyue Huang. Fast and accurate neural word segmentation for Chinese. IN proceedings of the 55th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers)
16. Martin Sundermeyer, Ralf Schlüter, and Hermann Ney. LSTM Neural Networks for language modeling. In INTERSPEECH, 2012.
17. [Sha and Pereira2003] F. Sha and F. Pereira. 2003. Shallow parsing with conditional random fields. Proceedings of NAACL
18. WojciechZaremba, Ilya Sutskever, and Oriol Vinyals.2014. Recurrent Neural Network regularization arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.2329
19. Fast Neural Chinese Word Segmentation for Long Sentences by SufengDuan, JiangtongLi,Hai Zhao
20. Name Entity Recognition with Bidirectional LSTM-CNNS by Jason P.C.Chiu.Eric Nichol

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